

AUTOMATED EXTRACTION OF ANATOMIC LANDMARKS ON VERTEBRAE BASED ON ANATOMIC KNOWLEDGE AND GEOMETRICAL CONSTRAINTS

Jianhua Yao¹, Joseph E. Burns², Sasha Getty², James Stieger¹ and Ronald M. Summers¹

¹Imaging Biomarkers and Computer-Aided Diagnosis Laboratory, Radiology and Imaging Sciences, Clinical Center, National Institutes of Health

²Department of Radiological Sciences, University of California, Irvine, School of Medicine

ABSTRACT

The determination of anatomic landmarks is an essential step in modeling, shape analysis, segmentation, and registration of the spine, as well as in spine interventions. In this paper, we propose a method to automatically partition each vertebra into anatomic substructures and extract the relevant anatomic landmarks. Anatomic knowledge is integrated in geometrical modeling for the landmark localization. Each vertebra is automatically partitioned into four substructures, and 43 anatomical landmarks are identified. The locations were validated with manual annotation from medical experts. The results showed that the automatic landmarks agreed with manually labeled reference standard landmarks (1.9 ± 1.3 mm).

Index Terms— computer aided detection, vertebrae, anatomic landmark

1. INTRODUCTION

The vertebral column forms the central weight-bearing axis of the human body, and is composed of 33 vertebrae distributed in five sections: cervical (7), thoracic (12), lumbar (5), sacrum (5 fused), and coccyx (4). The vertebral column provides for three main functions: 1) weight-bearing column support for the upper body and head; 2) protection of the spinal cord; and 3) allowance for trunk movement through multiarticulated flexibility. The complex anatomic structure of the vertebrae enables these functions. A typical vertebra is shown in figure 1. It consists of a body, arch (pedicles and laminae), transverse processes, articular facets, and posterior spinous process.

The determination of anatomic landmarks is an essential step in computational spine analysis tasks such as spine modeling, segmentation, registration, and computer-assisted intervention [1]. Anatomic shape modeling [2] often requires landmarks to align the model and to compute statistical variation. Anatomic landmarks not only facilitate the construction of the model but also provide anatomic meaning to the model. In spine segmentation [3], landmarks are important to initialize the model and thus significantly

reduce the complexity compared to initialization without landmarks. In registration [4], landmark based techniques are often much more efficient and accurate than intensity-based techniques. Furthermore, landmarks also provide reference and coordinate systems for image guided intervention [5]. For instance, during lumbar puncture procedures [6], the space between the spinal processes of two adjacent vertebrae is located prior to insertion of the needle. In a computer-aided detection system for spine fractures [7], it may be desirable to know the spatial location of the pathology, and provide the physician with accurate localizing information for treatment planning purposes.

There is no prior work focusing solely on the extraction of vertebral anatomic landmarks. A few prior works have relied on landmarks for their specific applications. In most of these studies, the landmarks were extracted either manually or semi-automatically [8]. In this paper, we will present a technique to automatically partition each vertebra into anatomic substructures, and extract the salient anatomic landmarks from thoracic and lumbar vertebrae.

Figure 1. Vertebra Atlas

2. METHOD

The workflow is as follows. First, given a spine CT data set, the spine is automatically segmented and partitioned into vertebrae. Next, a triangular surface mesh is generated for each vertebra. Finally, each vertebra is partitioned into anatomic substructures, and anatomic landmarks are extracted based on prior knowledge and morphologic properties.

2.1 Vertebra segmentation and surface modeling

Spine segmentation is accomplished through thresholding, fuzzy connectivity, and anatomic vertebral models [9]. The spinal canal is first extracted using a directed graph search. Then a vertebral template is fit along the spinal canal. Finally, the spinal column is partitioned into individual vertebrae by detecting the intervertebral disks on sagittal and coronal curved planar reformations. Figure 2a shows the segmented and partitioned spine.

Figure 2. Spine segmentation and vertebra modeling
a) Segmented and partitioned spine column, the view is a curved planar reformation along the spinal canal in the sagittal direction. b) Surface model of a L2 Vertebra. c) Color-coded surface feature map. The color indicates the cortical density.

For each vertebra, we obtain its segmentation and compute its exterior surface using a marching cube method [10]. Since this paper focuses on anatomical landmark extraction, a medical student manually corrected the segmentation error using in-house software. Figure 2b shows a vertebra surface segmentation. Characteristic features, such as the cortical shell density, can be mapped to the vertebra surface. Figure 2c shows a color-coded surface feature map, where we assign each facet on the surface the density value of its corresponding cortical shell.

Figure 3. Vertebra coordinate system

Figure 4. Vertebra partitioning

2.2 Vertebra coordinate system and partitioning

Thoracic and lumbar vertebrae consist of several typical components: the vertebral body, which is the main axial load-bearing portion of a vertebra; the transverse processes;

the posterior spinous process; pedicles; laminae; and articular processes. We develop a method to automatically partition a vertebra into four major components: body, left transverse process, right transverse process, and posterior spinous process.

We define a local coordinate system F for the vertebra $(O, \vec{X}, \vec{Y}, \vec{Z})$, where O is the origin and $\vec{X}, \vec{Y}, \vec{Z}$ are three orthogonal axes. Figure 3 illustrates the coordinate system. The centerline of the spinal canal (L , which is detected in the stage of spine segmentation) is used to set up the coordinate system. The intersects of superior and inferior disk planes with L , noted as c_1 and c_2 , are computed first. O is set as the middle point of c_1 and c_2 , $O = (c_1 + c_2) / 2$. \vec{Z} is set as the tangent direction of L at O . The XY plane is then determined by O and \vec{Z} . To define \vec{Y} , we locate the anterior tip t of the vertebral body surface by finding the surface point on the XY plane with largest distance from O in a restricted region ($\pm 45^\circ$ from direction vector $(0, -1, 0)$), i.e., $t = \operatorname{argmax} |t - O|$, where t is on the XY plane and $(t - O) \cdot (0, 1, 0) > \pi/4$. \vec{Y} is then set as $\vec{Y} = t - \vec{O}$. \vec{X} is then derived from \vec{Y} and \vec{Z} by the orthogonal rule. After F is established, the vertebra surface is transformed to the local coordinate system. The coordinates referred in the rest of the paper are all relative to F .

We partition the vertebra by finding the cutting planes through left and right pedicles and laminae. As shown in Figure 1, pedicles and laminae form the posterior arch of vertebrae. The vertebral bodies, in combination with the posterior arches, form the bony spinal canal which houses and protects the spinal cord. Pedicles and laminae predominantly consist of cortical bone and are the densest elements of the vertebra, per unit volume. Based on this anatomical attribute, we search for the cutting planes through pedicles and laminae based on CT density values. Without loss of generality, the left pedicle cutting plane is defined by $\Omega_{lp} = (p_{lp}, \vec{N}_{lp})$, where p_{lp} is the center of the cutting plane and \vec{N}_{lp} is the normal. We search for the cutting plane in a restricted region where the mean density of the cross section on the plane and through the vertebra is maximal. The process can be written as $\Omega_{lp}: (P_{lp}, \vec{N}_{lp}) = \operatorname{argmax} \left(\operatorname{Intensity} \left(C(\Omega_{lp}, V) \right) \right)$, s.t. \vec{N}_{lp} perpendicular to \vec{Z} and $(p_{lp} - O) \cdot \vec{X} < 0$ and $(p_{lp} - O) \cdot \vec{Y} < 0$, where V is the vertebra volume enclosed by the vertebra surface, $C(\cdot)$ is the cross section on the plane through the volume, $\operatorname{Intensity}()$ is the mean pixel intensity on the cross section. Multi-resolution exhaustive search is adopted as the optimization algorithm. Similarly we can search for the right pedicle cutting plane (Ω_{rp}), left lamina cutting plane (Ω_{ll}) and right lamina cutting plane (Ω_{rl}) using the following equations,

$$\Omega_{rp}: (P_{rp}, \vec{N}_{rp}) = \operatorname{argmax} \left(\operatorname{Intensity} \left(C(\Omega_{rp}, V) \right) \right),$$

$$\text{s.t. } (p_{rp} - O) \cdot \vec{X} > 0 \text{ and } (p_{rp} - O) \cdot \vec{Y} < 0,$$

$$\Omega_{ll}: (P_{ll}, \overline{N}_{ll}) = \operatorname{argmax}(\operatorname{Intensity}(C(\Omega_{ll}, V))), \text{ s.t. } (p_{ll} - O) \cdot \vec{X} < 0 \text{ and } (p_{ll} - O) \cdot \vec{Y} > 0,$$

$$\Omega_{rl}: (P_{rl}, \overline{N}_{rl}) = \operatorname{argmax}(\operatorname{Intensity}(C(\Omega_{rl}, V))), \text{ s.t. } (p_{rl} - O) \cdot \vec{X} > 0 \text{ and } (p_{rl} - O) \cdot \vec{Y} > 0,$$

Figure 4 shows the partition of a L2 vertebra. Note that our transverse process partitions also include the articular processes.

Figure 5. Automated landmark extraction

2.3 Vertebra landmark extraction

We then extract a set of anatomic landmarks on the vertebra, to characterize the shape and generate precise anatomical reference points on the surface. The following are a list of 43 anatomic landmarks that are currently extracted using our method (the number in the parenthesis is the number of points in each landmark set): superior endplate (4), inferior endplate (4), mid vertebral body (4), left pedicle (4), right pedicle (4), left lamina (4), right lamina (4), left transverse process (3), right transverse process (3), posterior spinous process (3), mammillary processes (2, only in lumbar vertebra), superior articular facets (2), and inferior articular facets (2).

Landmark extraction is based on anatomic knowledge and geometrical constraints about a relative location in the vertebra local coordination system. The landmarks are identified in a sequential order.

For the landmarks on the superior endplate, first we find all points on the vertebral body partition that corresponding to maximal z value at every (x, y) coordinate, i.e., $S = \{x, y, z\} = \operatorname{argmax}_z v(x, y, z)$, s.t. $v(x, y, z)$ are points in the vertebra body partition. Then the point set S is fitted to a plane which is treated as the superior endplate. The four bounding points on the superior endplate are the four landmarks for the superior endplate. Similarly, the inferior endplate and mid vertebral body landmarks can be located.

The bounding box of the left pedicle cutting plane (detected in section 2.2) through the vertebra volume defines the four left pedicle landmarks. The landmarks for the right pedicle, left lamina and right lamina can be obtained in a similar manner.

Three landmarks are identified for the left transverse process: tip, superior ridge and inferior ridge. The tip is the surface point on the left transverse partition with smallest x coordinate, i.e., $p(x, y, z) = \operatorname{argmin}_x v(x, y, z)$, where

$v(x, y, z)$ are points inside the left transverse partition. Superior ridge landmark is defined as the point with maximum z coordinate within half distance between the origin O and the process tip, and the inferior ridge landmark is defined as the point with minimum z coordinate in the same segment. Similarly, the three landmarks for the right transverse process can be defined. Applying the same rules, the three landmarks for spinous process can be extracted where y coordinate instead of x coordinate is applied in the formulation.

The landmarks for left/right superior articular facets are defined as the point inside the left/right transverse process partition with maximal z coordinate, and those for the left/right inferior articular facets are defined as the point inside the left/right transverse process partition with minimal z coordinate.

The left/right mammillary process landmarks for lumbar are defined as the point inside the left/right transverse process partition with maximal y coordinate.

Figure 5 shows the automatically extracted landmarks on the vertebra surface.

Figure 6. Comparison of manual versus automated landmark extraction

3. Experiment and results

Our method was applied on 16 cases acquired at the University of California, Irvine Medical Center, between March 2013 and May 2013. The mean patient age was 23 ± 4 yrs. The cohort included 6 men and 10 women. The scanning parameters were: 1mm slice thickness at 120keV. The CT data covered the thoracic and lumbar spines, and included 16.5 vertebrae per study on average. The algorithm ran successfully on all 16 cases.

To evaluate the performance of the vertebra partitioning and landmark extraction algorithm, one radiologist and one researcher visually checked the partition and manually labeled the landmarks on five cases. The total number of vertebrae for evaluation is 83. A three-scale score (1-3) is used to qualitatively evaluate the partition performance, 1: good partition; 2: slightly off partition; and 3: failed partition. Visual inspection showed 4 out of 83 had slightly off partition where parts of articular processes were included in the posterior spinal process, the rest had good partitions.

To evaluate the accuracy of automated landmark extraction by the system, we developed a tool to allow users to electronically mark points on the vertebra surface, and store each point as an assigned landmark reference standard. The spatial separation distance between the manually picked

Figure 7. Spatial variation for manual marking vs automated extraction of landmarks, and inter-user variability

landmarks and computer extracted landmarks were used to assess the accuracy of the system. 15 landmarks that are relatively easy to be visualized and localized by users were selected for this experiment. Two users performed the manual labeling task, and inter-user variability was evaluated. Figure 6 shows comparative examples of manual landmark points projected graphically onto a vertebra as picked by the two users, and automatically extracted landmarks. The quantitative results, stratified by landmark for comparison, are shown in Figure 7. The average distance between automated marking and user 1 marking of the landmarks was 1.9 ± 1.3 mm, and that between automated marking and user 2 marking of the landmarks was 2.3 ± 1.3 mm. The average distance between user 1 and user 2 manual marking of landmarks was 1.7 ± 1.3 mm. Paired t-test showed no statistically significant difference between auto-user variability and inter-user variability ($p=0.18$).

4. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we present a technique to automatically partition the vertebra and extract its anatomical landmarks. The technique is robust and its accuracy is comparable to inter-observer variation. The proposed technique can greatly facilitate computational spine applications such as registration and image guided intervention.

5. ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

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6. REFERENCES

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